

Synthesis and biological activities of some 2-(substituted-phenyl)-2-methyl-4-(1,2,4-triazole-1-yl)methane-1,3-dioxolane derivatives

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The seven new triazole compounds containing 1,3-dioxolane were designed and synthesized. Their structures were identified by means of elemental analysis, IR, ^1H NMR and MS spectra. The results from the primary biological test show that all the compounds have some activities of fungicide and plant growth regulator. When substituting group is 2,4-dichlorophenyl, compounds **2d** and **2f** show better biological activities, and suggests the better comprehensive efficiency prospect.

Triazole compounds have attracted much attention having been used as high efficient and wide spectrum fungicide and plant growth regulator¹. At present, the studies on triazole derivatives are mainly concentrated on compounds with triazole as the only active group. The report of triazole compounds that contain both triazole group and other active group in a single molecule has rarely been found. The triazole compounds containing 1,3-dioxolane have the remarkable prevention of the control over plant diseases². Propiconazol and difenoconazole are two important representatives. But the necessary intermediate for synthesizing propiconazol depends on imports, which leads to the cost of production and application too high. According to the concept of bioisosterism³, seven novel triazole compounds containing 1,3-dioxolane were synthesized. The biological activities of these compounds were tested. Also, their structures were determined by means of IR, EA, ^1H NMR and MS spectra. The synthesis route is described as follows :

R = H (**2a**); 4-Cl (**2b**); 2,5-Cl₂ (**2c**); 2,4-Cl₂ (**2d**); 4-ClPhCH₂O (**2e**); 2,4-Cl₂PhCH₂O (**2f**); 2-ClPhCH₂O (**2g**)

Results and discussion

Compounds **2a-g** were screened for their fungicidal activities against *Pratylenchus zae*, *Alternaria solani*, *Phomopsis asparagi*, *Physalospora piricola* and *Ceroxpora archidicala* at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration following agar plate diffusion method⁴ and compared with triazolone. Compounds **2b**, **2c**, **2d** and **2f** all exhibit some better efficiency on *Pratylenchus zae*, *Alternaria solani*, *Phomopsis asparagi*, *Physalospora piricola* and *Ceroxpora archidicala*. The fungus-inhibiting activities of compound **2d** against *Alternaria solani*, *Phomopsis asparagi* and *Ceroxpora archidicala* reach to 81.5–97.4%. The plant growth regulator activities of compounds **2a-g** have also tested towards *Wheat coleoptile elongation*, *Rooting of cucumber cotyledon* and *Rape hypocotyls inhibition* at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and compared with triazolone. Compounds **2d** also show the remarkable growth-promoting activity of 300% on *Rooting of cucumber cotyledon*. As far as the relation of structure and activity is concerned, when R group is 2,4-dichlorophenyl, compounds **2d** and **2f** show the best activity.

On the whole, the structure of compounds **2a-d** has an advantage in biological activity. On the other hand, group R has a significant effect on both fungus-inhibiting and plant growth regulating activities. The activity order can be listed as follows : 2,4-Cl₂C₆H₃ > 2-5-Cl₂C₆H₃ ~ 4-ClC₆H₄ > 2-ClC₆H₄ > Ph. Meanwhile, it can be seen from Table 1 that the relationship changes between structure and activity are not regular.

Note

Table 1. The fungicidal and plant growth regulator activities of compounds **2a–2g**

Compd.	Fungicidal activities (c = 0.005%, inhibition)					Plant growth regulator activities (c = 0.001%)		
	<i>P. zeae</i>	<i>A. solani</i>	<i>P. asparagi</i>	<i>P. piricola</i>	<i>C. arachidicala</i>	<i>Wheat coleoptile elongation</i>	<i>Rooting of cumcumber cotyledon</i>	<i>Rape hypocotyls inhibition</i>
	2a	17.6	15.8	0	11.5	4.5	0	+166.7
b	29.4	15.8	63.6	50.0	45.5	-7.4	+66.7	-4.5
c	23.5	10.5	81.8	38.5	45.5	-4.6	-33.3	-3.2
d	32.4	97.4	90.9	15.4	81.5	-0.9	+300.0	-1.8
e	0	0	0	35.4	0	-3.9	+31.7	-19.3
f	42.3	38.7	33.3	73.0	30.8	-3.9	+31.7	-10.2
g	7.7	0	0	30.8	0	-10.1	+69.3	-8.9
Triazolone	46.2	0	22.5	64.6	0	-24.0	+50.2	-64.2

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade and used directly without further purification. The 4-(substitution-phenylmethoxy)acetophenone was prepared according to the literature⁵. Elemental analyses were done with a Perkin-Elmer 1400C analyzer. IR spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) in KBr pellets, were recorded on a Nicolet FT-IR 170X spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were measured with a JEOL FX-90Q nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometer (CDCl₃ as solvent, TMS as internal standard). The melting points were determined on a Yanaco MP-500 melting point apparatus. The MS spectra were taken on a HP-5988A spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of intermediate (1) : To a 250 ml flask 0.02 mol substituting acetophenone in 50 ml of benzene, 0.08 mol anhydrous 3-chloro-1,2-propanediol and 0.1 g toluene-*p*-sulfonic acid were added. The reaction was refluxed and removed water for 5 h, and cooled to room temperature. Organic layer was washed with saturated sodium bicarbo-

nate solution, and then was successively washed with water to neutral, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtrate was concentrated above organic phase. The physical and elemental analyses data of seven intermediates (**1**) are list in Table 2.

Synthesis of compounds (2) : To a 100 ml flask 0.015 mol triazole, 25 ml DMF were added. Then mixture of sodium methoxide and methanol was dropwise added with stirring at about 18° for 0.5 h. The methanol and part of DMF were distilled by increasing the temperature to 140°. Distillation was stopped beyond 140° and the residual solution was cooled to 60° and to it added 0.01 mol intermediate (**1**) and 0.1 g of KI. The mixture was heated and refluxed for 3 h, and then poured into the ice-water under vigorous stirring, crude precipitate was purified by flash column chromatography (silica gel, using *V*_{petroleum ether} : *V*_{acetic ether} = 3 : 1 as eluent) to afford the required seven compounds. The physical and elemental analysis data of title seven compounds are listed in Table 3.

Table 2. The physical and analytical data of seven intermediates **1a–1g**

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p./°C or η_D	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
				C	H
1a	H	73.0	$\eta_D^{20} = 1.499$		
b	4-Cl	82.6	$\eta_D^{20} = 1.535$		
c	2,5-Cl	76.0	$\eta_D^{20} = 1.513$		
d	2-Cl	70.5	$\eta_D^{20} = 1.538$		
e	4-ClPhCH ₂ O	65.6	77–79	61.20 (61.19)	4.93 (5.10)
f	2-ClPhCH ₂ O	52.4	97–99	61.31 (61.19)	5.08 (5.10)
g	2,4-Cl ₂ PhCH ₂ O	61.3	89–91	55.96 (55.60)	4.75 (4.63)

Table 3. The physical and analytical data of compounds **2a**–**2g**

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p./°C or η_D	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
2a	H	51.4	$\eta_D^{20} = 1.527$	63.53 (63.66)	6.10 (6.16)	17.22 (17.13)
b	4-Cl	65.2	70–72	55.67 (55.82)	5.49 (5.54)	15.08 (15.02)
c	2,5-Cl	63.1	83–84	49.56 (49.70)	4.11 (4.17)	13.41 (13.37)
d	2,4-Cl	41.6	$\eta_D^{20} = 1.597$	49.38 (49.70)	4.00 (4.17)	13.59 (13.37)
e	4-ClPhCH ₂ O	45.7	132–134	62.29 (62.26)	5.27 (5.24)	10.84 (10.89)
f	2-ClPhCH ₂ O	25.3	130–132	62.31 (62.26)	5.25 (5.24)	10.83 (10.89)
g	2,4-Cl ₂ PhCH ₂ O	53.8	109–111	56.87 (57.14)	4.34 (4.52)	10.24 (10.00)

Table 4. IR and ¹H NMR data of compounds **2** and **4**

Compd.	IR (v/cm ⁻¹)		¹ H NMR	MS (m/z)
	C–O–C	C = N		
2a	1201, 1029	1505	1.58 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.81 (2H, m, CH ₂ N), 4.30–4.35 (3H, m, CH ₂ -CH), 7.25–7.38 (5H, m, C ₆ H ₅), 7.95 (1H, s, Tr), 8.27 (1H, s, Tr)	230, 168, 125, 105 77, 43
b	1217, 1010	1506	1.59 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.89 (2H, m, CH ₂ N), 4.30–4.36 (3H, m, CH ₂ -CH), 7.29–7.34 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄), 8.01 (1H, s, Tr), 8.41 (1H, s, Tr)	
c	1197, 1029	1507	1.71 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.90 (2H, m, CH ₂ N), 4.32–4.37 (3H, m, CH ₂ -CH), 7.24–7.51 (3H, m, C ₆ H ₃), 7.95 (1H, s, Tr), 8.29 (1H, s, Tr)	
d	1211, 1000	1509	1.69 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.82 (2H, m, CH ₂ N), 4.32–4.36 (3H, m, CH ₂ -CH), 7.23–7.43 (3H, m, C ₆ H), 7.94 (1H, s, Tr), 8.28 (1H, s, Tr)	
e	1242, 1176	1509	8.24 (1H, s, Tr-H), 7.96 (1H, s, Tr-H), 6.90–7.35 (8H, m, Ar-H), 5.02 (2H, s, PhCH ₂ O), 4.35–4.37 (3H, m, -CH ₂ CH-), 3.81–3.89 (2H, m, CH ₂ Tr), 1.60–1.61 (3H, m, CH ₃)	385, 303, 245, 178, 125, 120, 92, 89
f	1230, 1174, 1140	1507	8.24 (1H, s, Tr-H), 7.91–7.98 (1H, m, Tr-H), 6.90–7.42 (7H, m, Ar-H), 5.10–5.13 (2H, d, Ph-CH ₂ O), 4.35–4.63 (3H, m, -CH ₂ CH-), 3.81–3.89 (2H, m, CH ₂ Tr), 1.60–1.61 (3H, m, CH ₃)	
g	1235, 1176, 1138, 1056	1508	8.24 (1H, s, Tr-H), 7.96 (1H, s, Tr-H), 6.93–7.39 (8H, m, Ar-H), 5.15 (2H, s, PhCH ₂ O), 4.35–4.38 (3H, m, -CH ₂ CH-), 3.82–3.88 (2H, m, CH ₂ Tr), 1.60–1.61 (3H, m, CH ₃)	

Compounds **2a**–**g** were identified by means of IR, ¹H NMR and elemental analysis (EA). The IR and ¹H NMR and MS data of all compounds and EIMS of **2a** and **2e** are given in Table 4. All compounds show very strong absorption bands in IR spectra at 1240–200 cm⁻¹ and at about 1510 cm⁻¹, which are characteristic absorption bands for ν_{C-O-C} and $\nu_{C=N}$, respectively. The ¹H NMR data for all compounds are assigned. The molecular ion peak of compounds **2a** and **2e** in the mass spectra are very feeble or have not appeared, but all of the key fragment mass ion

peaks have appeared.

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